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of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

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The Heartbeat of the Hospital

Before the sun breaks through the glass
the halls are already wake
a soft drum of footsteps
the shuffle of charts
the quiet clearing of a nurse's throat

It isn't loud
but it's steadies
the heartbeat of this place

It rises from tired hands
that still choose to comfort
from calm voices that steady fear
from the small bravery of showing up again after a long night

Sometimes it sounds like a newborn crying
Sometimes like a whispered goodbye
Sometimes it's just the rustle of a blanket
being pulled up to someone's shoulders
because they looked cold.

No matter the hour it keeps going
in hope, in routine
in the simple kindnesses no one sees

This pulse felt more than heard
what holds the hospital together
people caring enough
to make someone's hardest day
a little easier

And that quiet rhythm stays with you
long after you step outside
into the noise of the world again.